

FINANCIAL LITERACY AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ATTITUDE OF NON-TEACHING PERSONNEL IN RELATION TO JOB PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION

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Financial Literacy and Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel in Relation to Job Performance: Basis for Intervention

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Abstract

The complexity of financial products and rising debt pose challenges for non-teaching personnel in educational institutions. Understanding how financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitudes affect their financial management and job performance is essential. This study examines the relationship between financial literacy, entrepreneurial attitude, and job performance among non-teaching personnel in selected public secondary schools in Negros Occidental. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study assessed the financial knowledge, behavior, attitudes, and training of the respondents, as well as their entrepreneurial mindset in terms of achievement, autonomy, creativity, risk-taking, and determination. A total of 135 non-teaching personnel participated in the study, providing quantitative data through standardized surveys and qualitative insights through interviews. Findings revealed that non-teaching personnel demonstrated high levels of financial literacy and positive entrepreneurial attitudes. Financial knowledge was particularly strong, while entrepreneurial drive and determination were prominent among respondents. However, financial training and entrepreneurial autonomy showed room for improvement. Job performance was rated high across all respondents, indicating effective workplace contributions. Statistical analyses showed that financial literacy varied significantly by sex but not by age, marital status, job position, or tenure. Similarly, entrepreneurial attitude did not significantly differ across demographic factors. Moreover, correlation analysis indicated no significant relationship between financial literacy and job performance, nor between entrepreneurial attitude and job performance. Despite this, qualitative responses suggested that financial awareness and additional income streams contributed to reduced financial stress and improved focus at work. The study recommends that educational institutions implement financial literacy and entrepreneurial training programs to enhance employees' financial decision-making skills. Future research should explore additional variables, such as financial stress and work motivation, to further understand their impact on job performance.

Keywords: *financial literacy, entrepreneurial attitude, non-teaching personnel, job performance, secondary schools*

Introduction

The increasing complexity of financial products and rising personal debt levels present significant challenges for working employees, particularly non-teaching personnel in educational institutions. As individuals are expected to take greater responsibility for their financial planning, there is a critical need to understand how financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitudes impact their ability to manage personal finances and job performance.

Improving the trend of enhanced financial management practices is critical, particularly for working employees, due to increased levels of personal debt and a growing emphasis on individual responsibility for financial planning. Employees' roles in managing their finances are increasingly difficult because of the complexity of financial commodities in the marketplace (Sabri et al., 2020). High quality of work life can give a result in better organizational performance, effectiveness and innovativeness (Daniel, 2020).

Effective financial management is essential for maintaining a high quality of work life, which in turn enhances organizational performance and effectiveness. Research has shown that financial literacy— financial literacy has been proven to affect both saving and investment behavior and debt management and borrowing practices (Lusardi, 2019). It involves not only knowledge but also the attitudes and behaviors necessary for sound financial decision-making (Zucchi, 2022).

Additionally, an entrepreneurial attitude, characterized by traits such as achievement orientation and innovation plays a pivotal role in how individuals navigate financial challenges and opportunities (Abun, 2019). An entrepreneurial mindset influences behavior and decision-making processes, which are essential for success in various contexts.

Despite the significance of these factors, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitudes of non-teaching staff within the Department of Education. While some studies suggest a positive correlation between overall income and well-being, few have explored how financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitudes relate specifically to job performance in this demographic.

This study aimed to address this gap by examining the levels of financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitudes among non-teaching personnel and their relationship to job performance. By focusing on these issues, the research sought to empower non-teaching staff to make informed financial decisions and adopt effective financial management practices. Furthermore, it aimed to provide educational institutions with insights to improve financial literacy and entrepreneurial initiatives that support the welfare of non-teaching professionals

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitude about the job performance of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in the 4th & 5th Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental. The results would serve as the basis for intervention. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub-questions:

1. What is the profile of the secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. marital status;
 - 1.4. job position; and
 - 1.5. tenure?
2. What is the level of financial literacy of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. financial knowledge;
 - 2.2. financial behavior;
 - 2.3. financial attitude; and
 - 2.4. financial training?
3. What is the level of entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel as a whole and in terms of:
 - 3.1. need for achievement;
 - 3.2. need for autonomy;
 - 3.3. creative tendency;
 - 3.4. calculated risk taking; and
 - 3.5. drive and determination?
4. What is the level of job performance of non-teaching personnel?
5. Is there a significant difference in the financial literacy among non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools based on their age, sex, marital status, job position, and tenure?
6. Is there a significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitudes of non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools based on their age, sex, marital status, job position, and tenure?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the level of financial literacy and job performance among non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the level of entrepreneurial attitude and job performance among non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools?

Literature Review

According to the findings of the study of Mercado (2023), most of the respondents belong to the prime working age (26-54 years old) group bracket. These are individuals that have the strongest attachment to the labor market while the least belong to the mature working age (55-64 years old) group bracket, these are older workers who are seen as giving a boost to an economy because of their greater work experience.

He also stated that the reasons for a higher proportion of female employees in the Philippines can be complex and multifaceted and having a higher proportion of female employees does not necessarily mean that an organization or industry is more diverse or equitable, as other factors such as representation in leadership positions and pay equity also play a significant role. However, Totenhagen et al. (2019) revealed that individuals who are married are less stable and more in debt compared to those who are single.

The research conducted by Janardhanan and Raghavan (2018) showed the critical role that employee productivity plays in the contemporary business climate. Specifically, high productivity requires a workforce comprised of high-achieving workers. This empirical study investigates the relationship between an employee's tenure in a business and their academic background and how it affects their ability to perform better.

Llona (2022) stated that tracking expenses significantly enhances employee financial awareness. Participants noted that by keeping track of their spending, they became more conscious of their financial habits, which allowed them to adjust their behaviors towards more responsible spending. This increased awareness led to improved financial stability and better decision-making regarding their finances, ultimately fostering a sense of security and well-being among the staff.

In the study on financial literacy, Tilan and Cabal (2021) found out that the teachers and other employees are knowledgeable in all factors of financial literacy. Furthermore, according to Khawar and Sarwar (2021) in able to make sound financial judgments, a person should be furnished with superior knowledge and attitudes. Financial literacy requires a high degree of financial knowledge. People who have insufficient financial knowledge will have difficulty managing their finances.

On entrepreneurial attitude, the findings of Abun et al. (2019) displayed that an entrepreneurial attitude was highly valued, particularly

in the areas of need for achievement, willingness to take calculated risks, and drive and determination.

The study of LeBoeuf (2022) posited that an entrepreneurial mindset cultivates resilience and adaptability, essential traits in today's dynamic job market. Non-teaching personnel who embrace these qualities are better equipped to navigate financial challenges, such as job insecurity or unexpected expenses. This adaptability can lead to sustained financial health, as individuals are more likely to pivot and find solutions in changing circumstances.

Several studies were conducted on work performance. Ramadhan (2020) found that there is a substantial influence of compensation on work performance, Rinny, Purba, and Handiman (2020) found the positive influence of promotion on work performance, and Norlina et al. (2020) confirmed the positive effect of work environment on job performance. In the same way, Morrow (2020) clarified that worker motivation can raise output and performance levels at work.

The findings of Strough et al.'s (2019) study found that older age was linked to higher self-reported use of domain-general experience in decision-making and that higher experience was linked to non-normative preferences for making financial payments. Even while they did not find any indication that experience accounted for older people's non-normative decisions, the results suggested that experience might play a key role in financial decision-making. Older age was significantly correlated with more financial experience, which confirmed earlier findings that older age was associated with stronger experience-based financial knowledge (Eberhardt et al., 2018).

Tuzi (2019) argued that young men reflected more on handling risk, being willing to act, and reading to increase their financial literacy than young women. Young women, on the other hand, were more preoccupied with matters linked to money management and how to spend it. This is congruent with the findings in the study of Minelgaite et al. (2022) which states that women are less financially literate than males, but there is no proof that this is because men and women have different interests in persons and objects. According to Totenhagen et al. (2019), individuals who are married are less stable and more in debt compared to those who are single. Moreover, Curto and Bown (2022) found that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure.

In addition, the study by Kobliner (2019) concluded that young personnel at twenty-five understand the fundamentals of money, and many of their money habits are established by the time they are thirty years old wherein they are wise and scared to have a bigger debt. But there are also fifty and above years old who are still aware and have no sense of understanding regarding financial literacy and end up loaning higher amounts each year.

According to the study by Mansour (2019), males have a greater attitude toward entrepreneurship than females do. Moreover, the findings of this study by Bual et al. (2024) presented that whether they are single or married, their marital status does not appear to have a substantial impact on their entrepreneurial behavior in terms of investment. Curto and Bown (2022) posited that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure. Furthermore, the study of Balitor et al. (2021) concluded that the job performance rating of the employees is not dependent on the financial management practices or status of the employees.

The study conducted by Mark-Margrove and Smith (2018) presented various stressors, including workload, job insecurity, and interpersonal conflicts, which collectively contributed to feelings of anxiety. The results indicated that stress adversely affected their productivity and job satisfaction, leading to a cycle of increased anxiety and decreased performance.

The result of the study of Bual et al. (2024) showed that although non-teaching personnel are generally content with their financial situation and demonstrate positive financial behaviors, there are opportunities for them to be more financially stable and gain a deeper understanding of financial concepts and products without compromising their works.

Boonsiritomachai and Sudon (2022) stated that an entrepreneurial mindset considerably and favorably influences work engagement, even though it may cause employees to lose focus on their degree of dedication. The study concluded that even extremely entrepreneurial employees would commit to an organization if they interacted with it.

Methodology

Research Design

This study examined financial literacy, entrepreneurial attitude, and job performance among non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools in Negros Occidental's 4th and 5th Districts. Using a descriptive-correlational design, it assessed these factors quantitatively while incorporating qualitative insights from interviews and open-ended surveys. The qualitative data enriched the findings by capturing personal experiences and perspectives, providing a deeper understanding of their influence on job performance.

Respondents

Using the total enumeration sampling method, this study surveyed 135 non-teaching personnel from secondary public schools in the 4th and 5th Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental for the academic year 2023–2024. The respondents included administrative and support staff, representing various roles essential to institutional operations.

Instrument

In this study, respondents answered questions through questionnaires and interviews. For the quantitative stage, two standardized instruments adapted from the study of Delmo et al. (2023) entitled “Financial Literacy and Financial Management Practices of Public School Teachers in Barangay Poblacion, Tantaran, South Cotabato” for the financial literacy, and from the study of Abun (2019) cited by Jocame (2019), Purbasari et al. (2021), and Cano et al. (2022) entitled “Measuring Entrepreneurial Attitude and Entrepreneurial Intention of ABM Grade XII, Senior High School Students of Divine World of College in Region I, Philippines” for entrepreneurial attitude and a self-made questionnaire for job performance were used which had undergone validity and reliability properly validated by experts. The survey instrument was divided into four parts. The first part pertained to the demographics of the respondents including age, sex, civil status, job position, and tenure of non-teaching personnel. The second part was the assessment of the level of financial literacy of the respondents using the 4 level scales: financial knowledge, financial behavior, financial attitude, and financial training. The third part of the survey questionnaire investigated the level of entrepreneurial attitude which includes the need for achievement, need for autonomy, creative tendency, calculated risk-taking and drive, and determination of non-teaching personnel.

The third part of the questionnaire focused on the job performance of the non-teaching personnel. The respondents were asked to rate each of these parts using a five-point Likert-type scale. Since the researchers utilized a self-made questionnaire modified by the need of the study to assess the level of job performance of non-teaching personnel, it underwent validity and reliability tests. In content validity, 3 experts were requested to rate each item. A validity index of 4.00 shows that the instrument was valid. After the establishment of its validity, a pilot test was conducted to 45 respondents indicating a reliability index of 0.856. It signifies that it is reliable.

Procedure

The researchers sought approval from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Negros Occidental to administer questionnaires among non-teaching personnel in secondary public schools. The request outlined the study's objectives, methodology, and potential benefits, emphasizing the importance of official authorization. Upon approval, the researchers prepared and distributed the questionnaires, ensuring respondents received clear instructions on the study's purpose, ethical considerations, and completion process to enhance response accuracy and reliability. To maintain data confidentiality, completed questionnaires were collected immediately after completion. Additionally, qualitative data were gathered through interviews with 10 non-teaching personnel, focusing on their financial knowledge, behavior, and attitudes. Following data collection, a systematic analysis was conducted to interpret the findings effectively.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers prioritized the privacy, confidentiality, and ethical treatment of all participants. In adherence to ethical research standards, respondents were fully informed about the study's objectives, methodology, potential risks, and benefits before providing their voluntary consent. Participation was entirely voluntary, with no coercion or undue influence. Personal data were handled with strict confidentiality and were not disclosed without explicit consent. The study maintained transparency and integrity throughout the research process, ensuring accuracy, honesty, and the avoidance of any form of deception or misconduct. Furthermore, all participants were treated equitably and with respect, upholding their rights, dignity, and well-being.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of Respondents

This section delves into crucial aspects such as age, sex, civil status, job position, and tenure offering insights into the diverse backgrounds of the study respondents. Table 1 on the next page presents the data.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	20 - 25 years old	2	1.48
	26 - 30 years old	30	22.22
	31 - 35 years old	31	22.96
	36 - 40 years old	13	9.63
	41 - 45 years old	27	20.00
	46 - 50 years old	13	9.63
	51 - 55 years old	12	8.89
	56 - 60 years old	7	5.19
	Total	135	100.00
Sex	Male	43	31.85
	Female	92	68.15
	Total	135	100.00
Civil Status	Single	45	33.33
	Married	89	65.93

	Widowed	1	0.74
	Separated	0	0.00
	Total	135	100.00
Job Position	ADA I - ADA VI	43	31.85
	ADAS I	2	1.48
	ADAS II	51	37.78
	ADAS III	13	9.63
	AO I	2	1.48
	AO II	14	10.37
	Guidance Counselor	3	2.22
	Registrar	3	2.22
	Accountant I	1	0.74
	AO IV	1	0.74
	Nurse II	1	0.74
	Librarian	1	0.74
	Total	135	100.00
Tenure	1 - 5 years	70	51.85
	6 - 10 years	39	28.89
	11 - 15 years	8	5.93
	16 - 20 years	6	4.44
	21 - 25 years	4	2.96
	26 - 30 years	8	5.93
Total	135	100.00	

A diverse age distribution among the respondents is shown by this demographic. Ages 20 – 25 represent 1.48 percent of respondents. Additionally, ages between 26 – 30 covered 22.2 percent of those interviewed while ages that range from 31 – 35 accounted for only 22.96 percent. Furthermore, ages ranging from 36 – 40 represented only a total of just equaling to about 9.63 percent. There are also those aged between the ranges of 41 – 45 years who were found to be around only 20 percent. Another, 8.89 percent were accounted for 51 – 55 years old, and finally, there are respondents aged between 56 – 60 years old who make up 5.19 percent of the sample population. There are fewest individuals in a group that consists of people aged between 20 – 25 years with just 1.48 percent of the respondents because the majority of them are older than them—almost half are under thirty-five—and quite a small amount belongs to the younger generations.

The findings of this study revealed different results from the study of Mercado (2023) that most of the respondents belong to the prime working age (26-54 years old) group bracket. These are individuals that have the strongest attachment to the labor market while the least belong to the mature working age (55-64 years old) group bracket, these are older workers who are seen as giving a boost to an economy because of their greater work experience.

In the survey's demographic structure, the sex distribution shows that female participants were more represented at 92 (68.15%) of the total sample while males only accounted for 43 (31.9%). In fact, among 135 most respondents' female participants was the most who participated on the conducted research. The findings of this study showed similar results based on the study of Mercado (2023) which stated that it's important to note that the reasons for a higher proportion of female employees in the Philippines can be complex and multifaceted and having a higher proportion of female employees does not necessarily mean that an organization or industry is more diverse or equitable, as other factors such as representation in leadership positions and pay equity also play a significant role.

In the same way, the distribution of respondents' civil status shows a diverse sample composition. Mainly, single respondents represent 33.3 percent with 45 individuals in total. Furthermore, married individuals constitute 65.93 percent, amounting to 89 respondents; while widowed make up another 0.74 percent, corresponding to one respondent. It is important to note that this range of civil statuses emphasizes how intricate the surveyed population is and therefore opens ways for investigating how societal factors affect variables under study. This finding is in contrast with the study of Totenhagen et al. (2019), which revealed that individuals who are married are less stable and more in debt compared to those who are single.

The distribution of job positions among the survey participants indicates a balanced selection in the sample. Most (37.78%) were Administrative Assistant II (ADAS II) accounting for 51 respondents. Additionally, 43 (31.85%) were Administrative Aide I – VI (ADA I- VI) and two (1.48%) were Administrative Assistant I (ADAS I) in their job position. Another 9.63 percent accounting for 13 were Administrative Assistant III (ADAS III) and two (1.48%) were Administrative Officer I (AO I). Furthermore, 14 (10.37%) of the respondents were Administrative Officers II (AO II) while three (2.2%) respectively were Guidance Counselors and Registrars. Lastly, 0.74 percent accounting for one respondent respectively were Accountant I, Administrative Assistant IV (AO IV), Nurse II, and Librarian. The respondents are diverse in terms of their job positions, which means that they have various levels of workload that must be considered as a factor and investigated in more detail when analyzing research outcomes.

The distribution of tenure among the survey respondents indicates a balanced selection in the sample. Seventy or 51.85 percent of the respondents were 1 – 5 years in the industry while 28.89 percent (39) of the respondents were working 6 – 10 years. Another 5.93 percent of employees who worked 11 – 15 years accounted for eight respondents while 4.44 percent (6) worked 16 – 20 years. Lastly, 2.96 percent (4) were employed in 21 – 25 years while 5.93 percent (8) were employed in 26 – 30 years. This indicates that most of the respondents were employed in the company for 1 – 5 years. This interprets that the employees were so dedicated to their work that they can afford to reach such a length of service. The present study's findings are consistent with the research conducted by Janardhanan and Raghavan (2018), which demonstrated the critical role that employee productivity plays in the contemporary business climate. Specifically, high productivity requires a workforce comprised of high-achieving workers. This empirical study investigates the relationship between an employee's tenure in a business and their academic background and how it affects their ability to perform better.

Level of Financial Literacy of the Non-Teaching Personnel

The table below reveals the financial literacy of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in the 4th and 5th Districts of Division of Negros Occidental when taken as a whole and when grouped according to financial knowledge, financial behavior, financial attitude and financial training.

Table 2. *Level of the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel*

<i>Financial Literacy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Financial Knowledge	4.45	Very High
Financial Behavior	3.45	High
Financial Attitude	3.83	High
Financial Training	4.10	High
As a whole	3.96	High

Table 2 indicates the different indicators of financial literacy of the respondents and when taken as a whole. The indicators included were evaluated individually and were analyzed as a whole. The financial knowledge got the highest mean of 4.45 and was interpreted as very high. This implies that employed secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel know the basic concept of money, the time value of money, and the level of risk attached to their financial decisions.

In terms of financial behavior, the mean score is 3.45 which was interpreted as high. This suggests that respondents generally engage in positive financial behaviors, such as budgeting and saving, although there may still be room for improvement. Furthermore, the interpretation also ascertained that the employed secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel have high perceived expertise in evaluating financial aspects.

As reflected in the table, the financial attitude is also interpreted as high with a mean value of 3.83. This shows that respondents have a positive attitude towards managing their finances and likely recognize the importance of good financial practices. Furthermore, the interpretation also ascertained that the respondents have high perceived expertise in evaluating learning financial aspects.

The interpretation of financial training is the same as the previous financial literacy indicators. The mean value is 4.10 and is interpreted as high. This means that the employed secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel have received substantial financial training, which likely contributes to their high financial knowledge and positive financial behaviors.

When all of the indicators are taken as a whole, the mean value is 3.96 which is interpreted as high. This result indicates that the respondents have strong financial literacy in the respective areas stated above. The importance of educating financial attitude to the secondary public school's non-teaching personnel is very significant for them to know and make themselves aware of financial budgeting.

This is congruent with the findings of the study of Llona (2022) which stated that tracking expenses significantly enhances employee financial awareness. Participants noted that by keeping track of their spending, they became more conscious of their financial habits, which allowed them to adjust their behaviors towards more responsible spending. This increased awareness led to improved financial stability and better decision-making regarding their finances, ultimately fostering a sense of security and well-being among the staff.

The findings of this study showed similar results based on the study of Tilan and Cabal (2021) wherein they found out that the teachers and other employees are knowledgeable in all factors of financial literacy.

Furthermore, according to Khawar and Sarwar (2021) in able to make sound financial judgments, a person should be furnished with superior knowledge and attitudes. Financial literacy requires a high degree of financial knowledge. People who have insufficient financial knowledge will have difficulty managing their finances.

Level of Entrepreneurial Attitude of the Non-Teaching Personnel

The table below reveals the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in the 4th and 5th Districts of Division of Negros Occidental when taken as a whole and when grouped according to the need for achievement, need for autonomy, creative tendency, calculated risk-taking, drive, and determination.

Table 3. *Level of the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel*

<i>Entrepreneurial Attitude</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Need for Achievement	3.82	Positive
Need for Autonomy	3.09	Neutral
Creative Tendency	3.15	Neutral
Calculated Risk-Taking	3.48	Positive
Drive and Determination	4.06	Positive
As a whole	3.52	Positive

Table 3 shows that among the respondents, drive and determination have the highest mean of 4.06 on the entrepreneurial attitude which is interpreted as positive. This suggests that respondents are highly motivated and determined to succeed in their endeavors. This was followed by the need for achievement interpreted as positive with a mean of 3.82 indicating that respondents generally have a strong desire to achieve and set high goals for themselves. Calculated risk-taking on the other hand is interpreted as positive as well with a mean of 3.48 indicating that the respondents are generally willing to take risks, but they prefer to do so in a calculated and thoughtful manner.

Meanwhile, creative tendency is interpreted as neutral with a mean of 3.15, suggesting that the respondents have a moderate desire for independence and control over their work, but it is not particularly strong. Lastly, the need for autonomy with a mean of 3.09 obtained the lowest which is interpreted as neutral. This suggests that the respondents have a moderate desire for independence and control over their work, but it is not particularly strong.

When all of the indicators are taken as a whole, the interpretation is positive which corresponds to the mean of 3.52. The interpretation opens the idea that the respondents have a positive entrepreneurial attitude. However, further implications based on the data suggest in terms of creative tendency and need for autonomy that there should be interventions to support the non-teaching personnel in enhancing their job satisfaction, motivation, and overall performance.

The results are in line with the findings of Abun et al. (2019) that an entrepreneurial attitude was highly valued, particularly in the areas of need for achievement, willingness to take calculated risks, and drive and determination.

This is congruent with the findings of the study of LeBoeuf (2022) which stated that an entrepreneurial mindset cultivates resilience and adaptability, essential traits in today's dynamic job market. Non-teaching personnel who embrace these qualities are better equipped to navigate financial challenges, such as job insecurity or unexpected expenses. This adaptability can lead to sustained financial health, as individuals are more likely to pivot and find solutions in changing circumstances

Level of Job Performance of Non-teaching Personnel

The table below shows the level of job performance of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in the 4th and 5th Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental.

Table 4. *Level of Job Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel*

<i>Level of Job Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Very High	70	4.18	High
High	61		
Moderate	3		
Low	1		
Very Low	0		
Total	135		

The table indicates that the majority of the 135 respondents fall into the very high and high job performance categories, both with a mean score of 4.18. The data suggest that the respondents are performing at a high level overall. This high level of performance can be attributed to factors such as effective financial management, strong entrepreneurial attitudes, and overall job satisfaction, as suggested by the previous tables on financial literacy and entrepreneurial attitude. The high-performance levels indicate that the respondents are contributing positively to their organization and are likely to maintain or improve their performance over time with continued support and development.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of Ramadhan (2020) regarding the substantial influence of compensation on work performance, Rinny, Purba, and Handiman (2020) regarding the positive influence of promotion on work performance, and Norlina et al. (2020) regarding the positive effect of work environment on job performance. In the same way, Morrow (2020) clarified that worker motivation can raise output and performance levels at work.

Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Age

The table below shows the difference in the financial literacy of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to age.

Table 5.1. *Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Age*

Age	n	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
20 - 25 years old	2	16.75			
26 - 30 years old	30	67.83			
31 - 35 years old	31	63.90			
36 - 40 years old	13	74.81			
41 - 45 years old	27	65.96	5.53	0.596	Accept Ho
46 - 50 years old	13	79.69			
51- 55 years old	12	69.25			
56 - 60 years old	7	72.86			
Total	135				

Kruskal Wallis was utilized to determine if significant differences exist between the variables. Results show that there is no significant difference in the financial literacy across the bracket of ages ($H=5.53$, $p=0.596$). These findings show that the age brackets did not significantly affect the financial literacy of public schools’ non-teaching personnel.

The findings of this study bear similar implications to those of Strough et al.’s (2019) study, which found that older age was linked to higher self-reported use of domain-general experience in decision-making and that higher experience was linked to non-normative preferences for making financial payments.

Even while they did not find any indication that experience accounted for older people’s non-normative decisions, the results suggested that experience might play a key role in financial decision-making. Older age was significantly correlated with more financial experience, which confirmed earlier findings that older age was associated with stronger experience-based financial knowledge (Eberhardt et al., 2018).

Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Sex

The table below shows the difference in the financial literacy of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel when grouped according to sex.

Table 5.2. *Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean Rank	U	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Male	43	56.44			
Female	92	73.40	1481.00	0.019	Reject Ho
Total	135				

The Mann Whitney U test was utilized to determine the difference in the financial literacy in terms of sex. Results revealed that the mean rank of females ($MR=73.40$) was significantly higher compared to the mean rank obtained in male ($MR=56.44$), ($U=1481.00$, $p= 0.019$). Since the p-value is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Rejecting the null hypothesis means that there is a significant difference in the financial literacy concerning sex. The financial literacy of both males and females is not par and there is a distinction that sets apart the two indicators. With these results, it can be noted that sex influence the financial literacy of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel.

These findings are congruent with the study of Tuzi (2019) which states that young men reflected more on handling risk, being willing to act, and reading to increase their financial literacy than young women. Young women, on the other hand, were more preoccupied with matters linked to money management and how to spend it. This is congruent with the findings in the study of Minelgaite et al. (2022) which states that women are less financially literate than males, but there is no proof that this is because men and women have different interests in persons and objects.

Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Marital Status

Table 5.3 shows the difference in the financial literacy of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel when grouped according to marital status.

Table 5.3. *Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Marital Status*

Marital Status	N	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Single	45	66.68			
Married	89	69.14	1481.00	0.019	Reject Ho
Widowed	1	26.00			
Separated	0	0.00			
Total	135				

Kruskal Wallis test was utilized to determine if the marital status of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel influences their financial literacy. Results show that there is no significant difference across the civil status ($H=1.28$, $p=.0527$). These results allowed the decision of the null hypothesis to be accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the data stipulated above at 0.05 level of significance. These findings show that the marital status did not significantly affect the financial literacy of public schools' non-teaching personnel.

These findings are in contrast with the study of Totenhagen et al. (2019) which revealed that individuals who are married are less stable and more in debt compared to those who are single.

Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Job Position

Table 5.4 shows the difference in the financial literacy of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to job position.

Table 5.4. *Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Job Position*

<i>Job Position</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
ADA I - ADA VI	43	57.05			
ADAS I	2	51.25			
ADAS II	51	73.14			
ADAS III	13	88.12			
AO I	2	106.00			
AO II	14	70.39			
Guidance Counselor	3	54.17	16.81	0.114	Accept Ho
Registrar	3	49.17			
Accountant I	1	126.00			
AO IV	1	20.00			
Nurse II	1	14.00			
Librarian	1	81.50			
Total	135				

Kruskal Wallis test was utilized to determine if there is a significant difference in the financial literacy of public schools' non-teaching personnel when they are grouped according to their job position. Results show that there is no significant difference across their job positions ($H=16.81$, $p=0.114$) which directed the decision to accept the null hypothesis. These findings show that the job positions did not significantly affect the financial literacy of public schools' non-teaching personnel.

This result is incongruent with the findings of Curto and Bown (2022) that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure.

Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when Grouped according to Tenure

The table below shows the difference in the financial literacy of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to tenure.

Table 5.5. *Difference in the Financial Literacy of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Tenure*

<i>Tenure</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
1 - 5 years	70	71.55			
6 - 10 years	39	62.42			
11 - 15 years	8	76.13			
16 - 20 years	6	65.33	2.11	0.834	Accept Ho
21 - 25 years	4	59.50			
26 - 30 years	8	62.25			
Total	135				

Kruskal Wallis test was utilized to determine if significant differences among variables exist. After the application of statistical analysis and data treatment, results show that there is no significant difference across tenure ($H =2.11$, $p=0.834$) which directed the decision to accept the null hypothesis. These findings show that the tenure did not significantly affect the financial literacy of public schools' non-teaching personnel.

This finding is in disagreement with the claim of Curto and Bown (2022) that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure.

Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Age

Table 6.1 shows the difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to age.

Table 6.1. *Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Age*

Age	f	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
20 - 25 years old	2	62.00			
26 - 30 years old	30	73.27			
31 - 35 years old	31	61.68			
36 - 40 years old	13	68.08			
41 - 45 years old	27	65.80	1.95	0.963	Accept Ho
46 - 50 years old	13	73.23			
51 - 55 years old	12	67.29			
56 - 60 years old	7	75.00			
Total	135	Total			

Using the Kruskal Wallis test to determine if there is a significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitude when grouped according to the age. The statistical evaluation showed that the p-value ($H=1.95$, $p=0.963$) is higher than 0.05 level of significance. With these statistical results, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis. There is no significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitude when grouped according to the age of the respondents.

This finding is in congruent with the study of Kobliner (2019) which stated that young personnel at twenty-five understand the fundamentals of money, and many of their money habits are established by the time they are thirty years old wherein they are wise and scared to have a bigger debt. But there are also fifty and above years old who are still aware and have no sense of understanding regarding financial literacy and end up loaning higher amounts each year.

Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Sex

The table below shows the difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to sex.

Table 6.2. *Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean Rank	U	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Male	43	66.15	1898.50	0.707	Accept Ho
Female	92	68.86			
Total	135				

The Mann Whitney U test was utilized to determine the difference in the financial literacy in terms of sex. The analyzed data revealed that the difference entrepreneurial attitude when grouped according to sex is not statistically significant at 0.05 level ($U=1898.50$, $p=0.707$). It can be noted that sex is not a determining factor as to the level of entrepreneurial attitude of the respondents.

The finding of this study is in contrast with the findings of Mansour (2019) study which indicated that males have greater attitude toward entrepreneurship than females do.

Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Marital Status

The table on the next page shows the difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to marital status.

Table 6.3. *Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel and Marital Status*

Marital Status	N	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Single	45	73.98			
Married	89	64.96	1.60	0.450	Accept Ho
Widowed	1	70.00			
Separated	0	0			
Total	135				

The p-value ($p=0.450$) is higher than 0.05 level of significance and the computed value is 1.60 using the Kruskal Wallis test. Based on these two results, the null hypothesis is accepted. The acceptance of the null hypothesis means that there is no significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to marital status.

The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of Bual et al. (2024) which stated that whether they are single or married,

their marital status does not appear to have a substantial impact on their entrepreneurial behavior in terms of investment.

Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Job Position

The table below presents the difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to job position.

Table 6.4. *Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Job Position*

<i>Job Position</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
ADA I - ADA VI	43	61.86			
ADAS I	2	96.50			
ADAS II	51	73.24			
ADAS III	13	61.19			
AO I	2	58.50			
AO II	14	69.21			
Guidance Counselor	3	38.33	13.08	0.288	Accept Ho
Registrar	3	77.00			
Accountant I	1	105.00			
AO IV	1	8.50			
Nurse II	1	117.50			
Librarian	1	133.50			
Total	135				

The computed value (H) according to the statistically-treated data is 13.08 while the p-value is at 0.288. With these results, the null hypothesis is accepted. The acceptance of the null hypothesis means that there is no significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to job position.

This is incongruent with the findings of Curto and Bown (2022) that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure.

Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Tenure

The table below illustrates the difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to tenure.

Table 6.5. *Difference in the Entrepreneurial Attitude of Non-Teaching Personnel when grouped according to Tenure*

<i>Tenure</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
1 - 5 years	70	74.38			
6 - 10 years	39	58.38			
11 - 15 years	8	60.88			
16 - 20 years	6	73.75	7.42	0.192	Accept Ho
21 - 25 years	4	37.88			
26 - 30 years	8	76.94			
Total	135				

The computed value (H) according to the statistically-treated data is 7.42 while the p-value is 0.192. With these results, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. The acceptance of the null hypothesis means that there is no significant difference in the entrepreneurial attitude of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel when grouped according to tenure.

This result is in contrast with the findings of Curto and Bown (2022) that the financial literacy and entrepreneurial levels of teachers and non-teaching personnel could be influenced by their job position and tenure.

Relationship between the Level of Financial Literacy and Job Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel

Table 7 on the succeeding page presents the relationship between financial literacy and job performance of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel in the 4th and 5th Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental.

As shown in Table 7, the Goodman Kruskal's Gamma Coefficient was used to examine the relationship between the levels of financial literacy and job performance of secondary public schools' non-teaching personnel. The result obtained negative and not significant correlations between financial literacy and job performance, $G=-0.07, n=135, p=0.648$. Based on these results, it was ascertained that there is no statistical relationship between the two variables This concludes that there is no significant relationship between the level

of financial literacy and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel and the null hypothesis was accepted.

Table 7. Relationship between the Level of Financial Literacy and Job Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel

Level of Financial Literacy	Level of Job Performance					Total
	Very high	High	Average	Low	Very low	
Very High	18	20	0	0	38	38
High	44	34	3	1	82	82
Moderate	8	7	0	0	15	15
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	70	61	3	1	135	135

Computed value (G): -0.07
 p-value: 0.648
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of significance

As shown in Table 7, the Goodman Kruskal’s Gamma Coefficient was used to examine the relationship between the levels of financial literacy and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel. The result obtained negative and not significant correlations between financial literacy and job performance, $G=-0.07, n=135, p=0.648$. Based on these results, it was ascertained that there is no statistical relationship between the two variables This concludes that there is no significant relationship between the level of financial literacy and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel and the null hypothesis was accepted.

The result of this study is the same with the implications of the study of Balitor et al. (2021) that the job performance rating of the employees is not dependent on the financial management practices or status of the employees.

Relationship between the Level of Entrepreneurial Attitude and Job Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel

The table presents the relationship between entrepreneurial attitude and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel in the 4th and 5th Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental.

Table 8. Relationship between the Level of Entrepreneurial Attitude and Job Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel

Level of Entrepreneurial Attitude	Level of Job Performance					Total
	Very high	High	Average	Low	Very low	
Very Positive	4	0	0	0	0	4
Positive	25	35	3	0	0	63
Neutral	41	26	0	1	0	68
Negative	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Negative	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	70	61	3	1	0	135

Computed value (G): -0.25
 p-value: 0.098
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of significance

As reflected in the table, the respondents with a very positive level of entrepreneurial attitude have scored very high (n=4) in the level of job performance. Additionally, the respondents with positive indicators of entrepreneurial attitude scored 25 interpreted as very high, 35 interpreted as high, and 3 in neutral. Meanwhile, the respondents with a neutral level of entrepreneurial attitude, 41 scored very high, 26 high, and one scored low in their job performance.

Goodman-Kruskal’s Gamma was used to examine the relationship between the levels of entrepreneurial and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel. The result obtained a not significant correlation between the level of entrepreneurial attitude and job performance ($G=-0.25, p=0.098$). The statistically treated data suggest that the null hypothesis is accepted. This concludes that there is no significant relationship between the level of entrepreneurial attitude and job performance of secondary public schools’ non-teaching personnel.

The result of this study is supported by the study of Bual et al. (2024) which stated that although non-teaching personnel are generally content with their financial situation and demonstrate positive financial behaviors, there are opportunities for them to be more financially stable and gain a deeper understanding of financial concepts and products without compromising their works.

Conclusions

Based on the study’s findings, the majority of respondents were female, married, and within the age group of 31-35, with most working as Administrative Assistant II/ADA II and having 1-5 years of experience. Their financial literacy levels were high, particularly in understanding money fundamentals, time value, and risk management. Additionally, respondents exhibited a positive entrepreneurial attitude, characterized by ambition, a drive for success, and a willingness to take calculated risks. Job performance was generally rated high, likely influenced by effective financial management, entrepreneurial traits, and job satisfaction. However, statistical analysis

showed that financial literacy differed significantly only by sex, with female respondents scoring higher than males. Entrepreneurial attitude showed no significant differences across demographic factors, and neither financial literacy nor entrepreneurial attitude had a substantial impact on job performance.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are proposed. The Department of Education may consider implementing financial literacy and entrepreneurial training programs to help employees manage financial challenges effectively. School administrators and human resource offices can introduce financial wellness programs that cover budgeting, debt management, credit use, and savings strategies. Additionally, school heads should incorporate financial education in in-service training and promote school cooperatives to support non-teaching personnel. Employees are encouraged to develop structured budget plans to distinguish needs from wants and allocate funds for unforeseen expenses. Lastly, future researchers should expand the study by including a larger and more diverse sample, considering additional variables that may influence financial literacy, entrepreneurial attitudes, and job performance.

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